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INTRODUCTION

PPMI

Overall Goal:
Identify Biomarkers of NSD/PD progression to accelerate therapeutics to slow disability

- Ø Biomarker signature that predict progression
- Ø Biomarker signature that identify disease subsets

Key PPMI pillars

- Ø Specific biomarker data set
- Ø Standardization of data acquisition and analyses
- Ø Open access/Data sharing

Study Synopsis

STUDY POPULATION N=5500	ASSESSMENTS/ CLINICAL DATA COLLECTION	BIOLOGIC COLLECTION	SHARED DATA & BIOSAMPLES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1100 PPMI current participants 700 PD 100 HC 300 Prodromal 1000 newly enrolled at clinical site 900 PD 100 HC 2000 Prodromal PD - Enrolled through staged risk (DAT deficit first) paradigm 1000 Prodromal PD - Enrolled through staged risk (syn SAA positive first) paradigm 500 PD Enrolled through staged risk (normoemic, syn SAA negative) Subjects followed for 5 to 18 years. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Motor assessments Neuropsychiatric/ Neurobehavioral testing Autonomic, orofaction, sleep DaTSCAN, HR - PET imaging sub-studies Digital data Online PPRs Online cognitive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DNA, RNA Serum, whole blood and plasma collected at each visit; urine annually Biosamples available; 200+ sample requests via BRC CSF collected at baseline and then annually IPSC in subset Skin biopsy Samples aliquotted and stored in central biorepository Post-mortem tissue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open-source data > 20 000 data downloads Biosamples available; 200+ sample requests via BRC Ancillary study opportunity Subjects followed for 5 to 18 years.

METHODS

PPMI - Comprehensive Longitudinal Phenotype

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|--|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clinical MDS UPDRS MoCA Neuropsych Battery Scopa-Aut Neuro-Qol RBDSQ STAI GDS | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Imaging DaTscan MRI sequences (resting stat, neuromelanin) PET substudies Synuclein SV2a DPA714 AV133 | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biofluid DNA/RNA (WGS) Blood - whole blood, plasma, PBMC CSF Urine Skin bx IPSC |
|--|---|--|

myPPMI - PPMI Participant Portal

myPPMI is designed as a simple strategy to bring all PPMI participant activities together.

- Everyone who has a PPMI ID can join myPPMI.
- Research opportunities are targeted based on existing participant data
- Research data is provided to participants
- < 200,000 PPMI Participants have received PPMI ID

Opportunities in myPPMI - current and in development

- PPMI assessments
- Cognitive testing
- Roche Digital
- PPMI Online
- Targeted enrollment - DEI
- Biomarker acquisition
- Info to Participants
- Return of research results
- Study outcomes
- Educational information

Biologic definition for Neuronal Synuclein Disease (NSD)

- Synuclein pathology - SAA
- DA Dysfunction - DAT imaging

Majority of participants enrolled with hyposmia or RBD and DAT deficit are syn SAA positive.

Group	SAA	DAT < 65%	DAT 65-75%	DAT >= 75%	Missing	Total
Hyposmic	Positive			1 (0.5%)		1 (0.3%)
	MSA-like					
	Positive	91 (85.0%)	48 (52.2%)	89 (44.3%)		228 (57.0%)
	Negative	16 (15.0%)	44 (47.8%)	111 (55.2%)		171 (42.8%)
Total	107	92	201		400	
RBD	Positive	2 (2.6%)		1 (0.9%)		3 (1.3%)
	MSA-like					
	Positive	67 (85.9%)	31 (75.6%)	77 (71.3%)		175 (76.4%)
	Negative	9 (11.5%)	10 (24.4%)	30 (27.8%)	2 (100.0%)	51 (22.3%)
Total	78	41	108	2	229	

NSD Integrated Staging System NSD-ISS (Simplified)

NSD stage	G+	ASyn (S)	DA Dysfunction (D)	Clinical Signs, Symptoms, Functional Impairment	
				Clinical Signs and Symptoms	Functional Impairment
Genetic risk (L vs H)					
R ⁺	G+ low risk	-	-	-	-
R ⁺	G+ high risk	-	-	-	-
NSD					
0	G+ (SNCA)	-	-	-	-
1A/B		+	-/+	+	-
2A/B		+	-/+	+	-
3		+	+	+	SLIGHT
4		+	+	+	MILD
5		+	+	+	MODERATE
6		+	+	+	SEVERE

Simuni et al, Lancet Neurology Jan 2024

*After year 1, the stage 2a group includes those in stage 2a or lower.

Longitudinal (5yr) change in NSD stage show that participants progress to higher stage over time

CONCLUSION

PPMI continues to enroll and follow participants to further investigate the biomarkers that define NSD stage and to utilize the NSD-ISS to accelerate therapeutic development throughout the disease course.

PPMI - a public-private partnership - is funded by the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research and funding partners, including 4D Pharma, Abbvie, AcureX, Allergan, Amathus Therapeutics, Aligning Science Across Parkinson's, AskBio, Avid Radiopharmaceuticals, BIAL, BioArctic, Biogen, Biohaven, BiLegend, BlueRock Therapeutics, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Calico Labs, Capsida Biotherapeutics, Celgene, Cerevel Therapeutics, Coave Therapeutics, DaCapo Brainscience, Denali, Edmond J. Safra Foundation, Eli Lilly, Gain Therapeutics, GE HealthCare, Genentech, GSK, Golub Capital, Handl Therapeutics, Insitro, Jazz Pharmaceuticals, Johnson & Johnson Innovative Medicine, Lundbeck, Merck, Meso Scale Discovery, Mission Therapeutics, Neurocrine Biosciences, Neuron23, Neupore, Pfizer, Piramal, Preval Therapeutics, Roche, Sanofi, Senvier, Sun Pharma Advanced Research Company, Takeda, Teva, UCB, Vanqua Bio, Verly, Voyager Therapeutics, the Weston Family Foundation and Yumanity Therapeutics.